

The Challenges of Teaching Costume and Scenic Design in Tertiary Institution: The Federal University Oye – Ekiti Experience

Mrs Lilian Eguriase **BAKARE**, (PhD)
Department of Theatre and Media Arts,
Federal University Oye Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria
lilian.bakare@gmail.com, (lilian.bakare@fuoye.edu.ng)

ABSTRACT

The basic responsibility of the theatre cast and crew, of which the costumier and scene designer are an integral part, is to interpret an artistic work. Thus, in communicating with the audience through costumes and scenic design, the ultimate goal of the costume cum set designer is to transform an ordinary person into an extraordinary yet believable character and setting within a story that does not exist in reality. Accordingly, costumes, as used in theater performances or movies, speak to the audience with words of silence and visual interpretation, just like the scenic design does. However, this study identifies a fundamental issue: the task of costume and set designers' interpretation presents a variety of challenges that they must overcome. This study therefore investigates the challenges of teaching costumes and scenic designs in educational theater, with a particular focus on FUYOYE Theatre. The study relies on semiotic theory to accomplish its goal, asserting that a costume/scenic designer constructs meaning based on a shared system of signification, which may originate from culture, a social system, or a belief system. The study employs qualitative research methods, focusing on literature analysis and examining the perspectives of scholars in the field. The study's findings confirm the challenge of teaching costume and scenic design in educational theatre. In light of the aforementioned findings, the study suggests that costume and set designers instruct theatre students in the fundamentals of costuming and design, emphasizing the importance of thoroughly researching the play before beginning the construction of costumes and sets. Also, costume and set designers must collaborate with the artistic team in the rehearsal process in order to achieve the team's success.

Keywords: Challenges, Teaching, Educational Theatre, Costume and Scenic Designs

1.1 Introduction

Costume is an essential feature of any dramatic production, and with makeup, coupled with scenic designs, it constitutes the total visual appearance of the actor. As Adakole Oklobia and Lilian Eguriase Bakare (p. 102) affirm, “a costume designer can suggest all manners of moods, ideas, and feelings.” Just like scenic design, a costume is more than just a mere covering or background for an actor; its essence lies in the actor's wear and play, their movements and speech, and their constant presence in the audience's attention. Costume assists characterization so that whether in film or on stage, the audience can determine age, social status, personality, nationality, dislikes, etc., before the character utters a word. Costume also helps to establish the relationship between characters; the actors and the costume interpret the character. We can no longer overemphasize the significance of costumes, scenic design, and characters in the production of plays. The reason for this is that costumes have evolved significantly and now play a crucial role in our daily lives. There is no culture, tribe, or country that doesn't have a costume. Without a costume, it would be impossible to identify a people group. The costume of a people, like their culture, is the hub around which revolves their worldview. People wear clothing not only for the comfort but for the information they want to give others about themselves. Just like culture, costume can be preserved. Different countries, each with diverse cultures, have their own unique costumes. Costumes tell more about a person or a particular tribe or country. For example, the Scottish men are known for putting on kilt skirts; the Africans have diverse costumes. The characters in the play represent the cast. They range from the extraordinary characters to the dominant characters and minor characters. Characters are integral to the production of a text or play, just like a costume.

Costumes have come a long way; they play a significant role in our lives. A play's costume determines its genre. It enhances the aesthetic value of the play. According to Lilian Eguriase Bakare (p. 407), “costume materials and designs ... make play performances meaningful.” The genesis of costume started from when Adam and Eve ate the forbidden fruit in the Garden of Eden; when they discovered that they were naked, they took leaves to cover themselves. Back-to-theater costumes represent the personal dimension of the visual element. People perceive the performer and the costume as one, merging into a single image on stage (Wilson 362). People don't just wear clothing for comfort, but also to convey information about themselves to others. Clothes have always signaled a number of things regarding the wearer, including the following:

1. Position
2. Sex
3. Occupation
4. Relative flamboyance

In the theatre, clothes send us signals to those in everyday life, but as with other elements of theatre, there are significant differences between the costumes of everyday life and theatrical costumes. Over time, scholars from different backgrounds have tried to give the meaning to costume in different ways. The Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary states that people from a particular place or during a particular historical period wear costumes to reflect their culture or events.

Berger defines the term "costume" as either the general wardrobe and dress, or the distinctive styles of a particular people class or period. Alternatively, it can refer to the artistic arrangement of accessories in a picture, statue, poem, or play, appropriate to the time, place, or other circumstances represented or described, or to a particular style of clothing worn to portray the wearer as a character or type of character other than their regular personnel at a social or cultural event such as a masquerade, a fancy dress party, or in an artistic theatrical performance. (142)

However, character analysis is another important element in theatre. It is simply the way a director/actor perceives a particular character in a play. By carefully emphasizing certain aspects of a character's personality while eliminating others, the dramatist can show us in two hours the entire history of a person, which it could take us a lifetime to know in the real world. For example, most modern creative writers have continued to use theater materials to blend their modern literary compositions. Obviously, communication in a play production is more dynamic and complex than in everyday life or any other art form. The play production engages in a verbal and nonverbal communication process, using costume and character as communication modes to convey meaning to the audience. To this end, Wilson posits that anyone who wants to understand how theater works as a form should be aware of the range and complexity of the symbolic communication that is necessary within even a single play or performance (367).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Costumes, scenic designs, and characters play a significant role in play production. Costume, on its part, tells the viewer the genre of the play, i.e., whether it is comedy, farce comedy, melodrama, etc. It also indicates the background of the play. Characters are the cast in the play; they range from the extraordinary characters to the dominant and minor characters. Without characters, a play cannot be produced. This study focuses on certain measures to avoid miscasting or misinforming the viewers. Also, the role of both elements is to convey meaning and interpret situations. The absence of proper costuming and scenic design in any production denies the audience the actual interpretation, message, and understanding of the entire play production. The challenges of this study are formed by the functions that coordinate these arts of the theatre, namely costume, scenic designs, and lighting, to ensure appropriate performance interpretation. In light of these challenges, this research delves into the difficulties associated

with teaching costume and scenic designs in tertiary institutions, with the goal of suggesting viable solutions to these issues.

1.3 The Art of Costuming: an Overview

Determining the role of the costume designer in defining the character of a production is a crucial question. This includes understanding designer tools and how they affect products. Every production in theatre is the culmination of a collaboration of creative individuals who each have a very explicit role to play in the process of creating each specific work of art. A theatre production would not realize its full potential without the work and research of set designers, lighting designers, directors, producers, and props masters. One of the most important components of a successful theater production is creating an illusion. The idea is to create a new world through characters to which the audience relates and through which they understand the idea behind the production. For the set designer, that means researching the setting of the story while still creating a functional area in which the actor can portray his art. The lighting designers utilize light to enhance the mood and direct the audience's attention to the intended spot. For the props masters, that means poring through the script to determine what items are necessary to the production and how best to construct them. For the costume designer, creating a new world for the audience means enabling the actor to better adapt to their role in order that he or she is better able to portray the character.

On the practical side, the costume designer clothes the actor and ensures that the actor is able to perform without constriction due to their costumes. It is important to understand what enables them to decide the best option of clothing for the actor in each specific production. In addition, an understanding of the creative process they need to implement allows them to interpret the character without sacrificing the script. Lastly, an understanding of the tools and devices that they use to reach the illusion set forth within the script is important to a successful final product.

1.4 Theoretical Framework

Semiotic Theory

Semiotic is the study of signs, symbols and signification. It is the study of how meaning is created, not what it is but how it is evoked. The revolutionary nature of semiotic can be summarized by saying that, in general it challenges the way Western civilization has conceived the world since Plato. Barthes (cited in Berger) took over Saussure's concept of language as a sign system, producing work that can be regarded as an appendix to his "Mythologies" (3), he shows how the denotations in the signs of popular culture betray connotations which are

themselves myths generated by the larger sign system that make up society. Adapting Saussure's model to the study of cultural phenomena other than language, Barthes developed his Fashion System (cited in Berger 4). In his Fashion System, Barthes shows how the adulteration of signs could easily be translated into words. He explained how in the fashion world any word could be loaded with idealistic bourgeois emphasis. Thus, if popular fashion says that a 'skirt' is ideal for a certain situation or ensemble, this ideal is immediately naturalized and accepted as truth, even though actual style could just as easily be interchangeable with a 'wrapper', 'bubu' or 'trousers' or any number of combinations.

Semiotics theory as it is related to this study tells us how the meaning constructed by a costume / scenic designers is a product of shared system of signification. For instance, the traditional Urhobo society denotes the wearing of two wrappers to signify that a woman is a wife and mother. Thus the signification of a woman's marital status by two ankle-length wrapper is a constructed meaning which has over time become the Urhobo culture. Again, semiotics can be defined as the study of signs: how they work and how we use them. Berger defines semiotics as "The science that investigates the way meaning is produced and transmitted" (244). While a sign is anything that can be used to stand for something else; for instance, using a white robe with cape and a cross pendant to signify a catholic priest.

1.5 The Essentials of Teaching Costume and Scenic Design

1. The Costume and Scenic Designer's ability to embark on thorough Research Process

The world of costuming requires the designer to investigate ways in which to achieve a desired illusion. This method varies from designer to designer, but there are several components to it that are necessary for every costume designer to follow. These components include the script, the theme, the time period, the character, the sketches, the tools, and the costume plot. The Script Research is imperative when designing for a production and it starts with a thorough reading of the production's script. Costuming may be a creative process, but it is still bound by the circumstance of the costume as prescribed by the script which includes such information as time period, and functional elements. The script is the costumer's playbook through which they start the creative process. Since knowing the script is a monumental prerequisite to the correct execution of a costume, it is necessary that the costume designer read it more than once. In fact, "familiarization (with the play script and its characters) can only result from a careful reading--and often re-reading many times--of the script" (Motley 11).

The first reading of the script gives a basic overview of the story behind it. Future readings consist of enhancing one's knowledge of the story more and also discovering various elements of the story that greatly affect not only the looks of the costume, but also how it is made, with what

it is made, and placement of its parts. Although, many other scripts provide much the same information in them with paragraphs specifically provided for the use of the costume designer in terms of what is required in certain scenes. Even so, the writer of a script is not required to provide the costumes; therefore, this information is provided at the script writer's discretion and serves merely as an aid for the designer to understand the vision of the writer for his characters in specific scenes. Out of all that the script provides, most important is the basic information vital to each member of the production team. For the costume designer, this is especially important in regard to quick changes. A quick change requires the actor to change costumes quickly from one costume to another based on scene or character changes. The information about the scenes provided in the script enables the designer to know which costumes need to be removed and replaced easily and which costumes can be more of a permanent fit. The script also provides the number of characters, the setting, the number of scenes, and the actions performed in each scene. These are all general ideas that factor into specific details of the entire wardrobe of the play.

A. The Concept: Though the script is full of relevant material for the costume designer, the next component of their trade deviates from what is put forth in the script and relies on the creative vision or concept of the director. The concept of the play is the director's take on the writer's theme in the production (Scarfone&Stillman 22). This idea translates to the costume realm where the vision of the director greatly affects the final result. From desiring the play to be very abstract to wishing for it to include a lot of lace, director's concepts play directly into the work that the designer does. It is yet another parameter within which the costume designer must express their own creativity and it is also another way in which the audience is able to read into the character through the director's eyes. In the same way, costume designers have their own concepts for their costumes. Both their creativity and expertise are required in order to cause their costume concept to coincide with the director's concept for the production. Though the director has a final say in a costume and gets to dictate certain aspects of costumes through their concept, the costume designer is able to work within those parameters to develop their own ideas and interpretation of the director's concept. The costume designer's concept is revealed through the way that they choose to clothe each character.

B. The Time Period and Geographical Location: After defining the concept, the costume designer must then translate this costume into the time period and geographical location of the play. Time period is integral that the move towards "attempts at historical accuracy in stage costuming" is actually credited to J.R. Planche (Richmond 233), a British playwright who authored over 175 plays. Realism in historical costuming was not considered to be important until "the first decades of the nineteenth century" (Richmond 233). Costumer Adrienne Martine-Barnes goes so far as to say that she became "rather an arrogant bore on the subject, though (she) never stooped to quite the rudeness of telling a woman in a Scaparelli pink satin Tudor she was out of period- however tempted (she) was" (25).

Defining a character within a time period enables the designer to communicate to the audience what the actor was going through in his or her lifetime. It communicates more than just a year or time frame, but delves into a study of prevailing views of a time and cultural norms for that time frame. This, then, not only educates the audience in the history of the time, but also sets the stage for the theatrical production. Therefore, the costume designer has to absolutely ensure accuracy to the period in which it takes place. This includes deciding such factors as whether or not ruffles were the prevailing fashion of the time. For example, "the Victorian lady wore gowns of prim, grayed hues while the Elizabethan lady was a splash of colour" (Paterek 28). This idea is predominant in the representations of the Shakespearean era plays and their strict interpretation.

Another example arises from men's suits. During the time of the setting of the musical *Mary Poppins*, the predominant male suit was either double breasted or a three button suit. In deciding costumes for such a production, historical accuracy requires that the costume designer keep this in mind for the men's costumes.

C. Geographical location is equally as important when creating the costumes for a play. Clothing styles are very different from country to country. For example, the costumes for the musical *Aladdin* are very different from those for *Oklahoma* no matter the interpretation. The costume designer must realize that the setting is just as important as the time period by perhaps even exaggerating the stereotypical nature of each country represented in order to obviate the nationality or location of each of the specific characters of a production. Thus, costumes must be used to enhance the heritage of the character wearing them. The Character "Through tattered clothes great vices do appear; Robes and furred gowns hide all. Plate sin with gold and the strong lance of justice hurtles breaks. Arm it in rags: a pigmy's straw does pierce it" (Shakespeare, *King Lear* 64). This quote is among many in which William Shakespeare attempted to convey the power of clothing to either hide or unveil a person's true character. In this quote, he compares the clothing of a character to his or her virtues. Thus, clothing speaks for the character. Out of all of the components that a costume designer must consider when creating or designing a costume, the character is the most important.

The script, the concept, the time period, and the geographical location set general parameters from which the designer interprets what a costume should look like. However, after these items have been set, the details of costuming are determined by additional factors such as mood, class, age, gender, and personality.

D. Mood and Colour: When costuming the character, the mood of the play affects the type of costume that the character should wear. A general overview of the storyline and the events of the production help the costume designer to define the mood of the play in order to clothe the character. After establishing the mood, one thing that helps to better express the mood of a character is colour. Since different colours signify different things, they help to expand the knowledge of the audience on the feel of a specific scene when purposefully placed on a

character. To reiterate, "Colour can carry important meaning and can have an important impact on people's affect, cognition, and behaviour" (Elliot para. 1).

Just like the physical appearance of a masquerade is a great determinant of its acceptance (Lilian E Bakare, p 408), in play productions, colours help the audience to instinctively feel a certain way about a character or about the production itself. In dark productions such as Sweeney Todd, dark colours that have been neutralized with cool greys and browns are used to clothe the actors. This, then, establishes not only a feel for the character himself, but also a feel for the production in general. Likewise, contrasting colours are used for contrasting characters. In *The Wizard of Oz*, the Wicked Witch of the West is portrayed in the age-old black witch's costume with a pointed hat while the good witch Glinda is arrayed in a "gown... made of layers of delicate pink tulle sprinkled with 'northern stars' and frosty snow crystals" (Scarfone and Stillman 84). This portrayal enabled the audience to tell the good character from the evil character right away simply by looking at the colours in which they were covered. Therefore, when creating costumes, it is important for the designer to understand what colours would best describe the mood of the character.

E. Class: Another important feature of a character that the costumer must remember to find a way to express in the costumes is the class or social status of the individual wearing the costume. For instance, if a princess wore the garb of a maidservant, the audience would spend more time trying to figure out the roles of the characters than focusing on the actual production. In order to direct the audience's attention, the costume must fade into the background and assimilate itself into the setting and character. In fact, costume designers Jerrard Smith and Diana Smith have written that "a designer's work is never meant to draw attention to itself but rather to be a part of the fabric of the whole theatrical presentation" (28). When expressing the facet of the character known as class, this fact is obviated. The actor must be able to show their station in life in the production and this is accomplished by a collaboration of the actor's abilities and the expertise of the costume designer in ensuring the accuracy or believability of that character's station in life or social status in their costume.

For the costume designer, research into this part of the character means simply reading the character's description and using that information to create the costumes. Besides keeping the audience focused on the production at hand, defining class is important in helping to establish historical accuracy. Some productions have very specific characters, who, in their original time period, would be required by sumptuary laws to wear a specific type of clothing. During the Middle Ages, servants were required to dress their station so that no one would mistake them for anything else. In fact, "the theaters proved to be the one place where the sumptuary laws largely succeeded in determining the apparel that people wore" (Lublin 43). Therefore, deviating from class dress would lessen the historical accuracy of a production.

F. Texture: When deciding on which types of materials to use when constructing a costume, "the texture of cloths is fully as important as the colour" (Lublin 54). The texture of the fabric used in a piece of clothing speaks volumes as to the monetary worth and station of a person in everyday life let alone in theatre. Laces and silks communicate affluence and wealth while burlap, plain muslin, and cotton communicate destitution and poverty. The costume designer should have a firm understanding of the looks that each kind of fabric has in the eyes of the viewer in order to correctly choose the types to use. Rough textures coincide with rough characters while soft textures coincide with soft characters. For example, a thief in a production would have cause to wear rough cottons while the affluent whom he was robbing would be clothed in satins. When a costume designer uses textures correctly, the audience unknowingly groups the characters wearing them into the certain class to which they belong, enabling them to define the character even more.

G. Age: A creative costume design should also suggest the age of the character. The age of the character can initially be determined by the costume designer by either the description given by the author of the play or by looking at the relationship of the characters in the play and reading the age cues therein. Many times, actors play in roles that are much younger or much older than the actors actually are or they play roles in which they age gradually. In any case, it is the responsibility of not just the makeup department, but also the costume designer to reflect this change in age. Through the use of colour, trimmings, patterns, etc. the costume designer can subtract or add years from an actor depending on the need for their character. Historically, children have been clothed in easily removable and simple clothing while seniors have chosen clothing that is both sensible and warm. Again, the most exaggerated of stereotypes in this area best represents what the costume designer is trying to communicate through his or her costumes. However, this must still be accomplished with as little ostentatiousness as possible. Also, with the use of trimmings such as bows for young girls and caps for young boys, accessories can be used by the costume designer to reveal a character's age.

I. Gender: A fourth consideration in designing the costumes for a production is the gender of the character that they clothing. This character detail is usually easy to realize by the costume designer in the names of the characters and is also usually defined by the script. In the past, men played all of the roles in plays and, therefore, were left to use specific methods to train the audience to understand their gender. One of these methods was by using costumes. In the earlier Shakespearean theatre, "before an actor... delivered his first words in performance, the audience would have seen how he was dressed and understood whether the character he was playing was male or female" (Shakespeare 1). Though this is not practiced very much today, there are productions in which the story calls for a man disguising himself as a woman or a woman disguising herself as a man. In these cases, it is important to use the correct styles of clothing in order to complete this portrayal. For example, in the play *Les Miserables*, the character Eponine disguises herself as man to sneak onto the battlefield. Without the proper attire, this

transformation would not work. However, using such tricks as loose clothes with rougher textures and more obviously the use of men's styled clothing, the transformation is possible for the costume designer and the effect causes the audience to grasp the situation much more easily.

J. Personality: The most important component when considering how to costume the character in the play is their personality. Though often confused with the identity of the character himself, the personality of the character has more to do with the temperament of the character. The costume is one of the biggest clue-ins for the audience as to the temperament of the wearer, even as it changes throughout a production. Unlike the rest of the factors regarding the character, the costume designer must really read into the script and know the specific characters before they can decide how the personality of the characters would affect what these characters would wear. After deciding what kind of character with which they are dealing, the costume designer is then able to decide what methods they would use in order to communicate that personality to the audience. For example, an obnoxious character could wear loud and ostentatious colors and styles while a quiet character could wear simple colors with little frills. This step of defining a character ends up being very much in the creative realm of the costume designer and is the area where there are few rules to dictate what the designer must create. However, even while expressing their creativity, the designer must remember every other component of the character that must be followed even in their creative designs. A good costume designer realizes that a costume is not just a costume. It is a reflection of the character on which it resides and must be "suited to the... personality of the wearer" (Lublin 37). If a character is sad, its costume should reflect that in dull and dark colours.

If it is an obnoxious and boisterous character, its textile's colours, patterns, and style should reflect the character's loud and obnoxious behaviour. For instance, a bright red fabric could be used for an antagonist while a subtle white and blue fabric could be used for a character with a particular innocence about them. "Costumes are invaluable in providing information to the audiences about the story and the character being presented" (Smith and Smith 29) and these costumes rely on the fabrics of which they are made in order to help accomplish that goal. The Sketches After the initial research, the designer is then able to start sketching their ideas based on the knowledge that they have gathered thus far. However, even in creating sketches, some amount of knowledge must be had regarding how certain fabrics cooperate with certain designs and how to draw specific design details in order to correctly express the costume designer's desires for the costumes. When sketching a clothing design, the design details must be apparent to all members who are involved in the construction of the costume being sketched. For every detail, there is a specific way of expressing it in a drawing. For example, complicated features such as transparency, gathered fabric, fabric creasing, and pleating require drawing skills beyond basic knowledge (Lovell 1011). Also, giving the costumed figure a 3-D form by using highlights, lowlights, and shadows helps those looking at the sketch to determine the best way to translate

from sketch to reality. Correctly learning these techniques helps the costume designer on the journey towards defining their character.

Besides learning to sketch design details, the costume designer must realize that certain fabrics act certain ways. For instance, thick wool will not gather easily. Therefore, if the costume designer is creating a design in which they desire to use thick wool, gathering it would not be a good idea. In this way, the costume designer must either base their fabrics off of their design or vice versa and still communicate this idea to those who are constructing the garment. Without this type of knowledge, a designer's concept for a character could easily get skewed by those lower down in the chain of command, thus skewing the audience's perception of the designer's concept. Depending on whether or not the designer has a design in mind first, this could also be a major factor in choosing the types of fabrics.

2. Teaching the Essential Equipments / Instruments: Sewing Machine, Needle, and Thread

Though very basic tools, in the hands of the costume designer, the sewing machine, needle, and thread literally hold together their costumes. Without these basic components, the spectacular displays of creativity that the costume designer is able to whip together would not be possible. Thus, even such a small tool can make a big difference in defining a character in a production through costume. The Costume Plot A costume plot is "a complete inventory... of everything that is required by the script and the designer for each character" (Emery 4). In other words, it is the organization of all of the costume designer's work put into one document. It spells out every costume and accessory that is to be worn by each character of a production in each and every scene in an orderly chart.

When creating costumes for productions, it is not always easy to remember who wears what when and how they wear it. However, it is still the job of the costume designer to make sure that each and every actor has the correct number of costumes for the correct scenes in each production for which they design. Therefore, costume designers use the costume plot to organize all of their work for the benefit of not only themselves, but also for the members of the production team whom it concerns and the actors who will be wearing the costumes. The costume plot's function is to enable others to decipher through the myriad of costumes and accessories available and find the ones that are intended for each character. Without a costume plot, it would be very easy for the costume designer to forget how many costumes are required for each character due to various events occurring during the production such as day changes.

3. The Essentials of Working with Cast and Crew and Time Schedule

"Theatre is a group art, and its highest expression comes through the combined efforts of a creative staff" (Paterek 2). This quote explains how humans are able to best express their

creativity as part of a group. Proverbs 15:22 says that "Plans fail for lack of counsel, but with many advisers they succeed" (New International Version). In the world of theatre, it is necessary that each member of the production team coordinate and cooperate with each other in order for the production to proceed smoothly and in order for it to bring the audience into the world of the theater and into the minds of the characters without a hitch. Specifically, the costume designer needs to work on the same time schedule as the rest of the team, which includes the director, the actors, and the other areas that are covered, by the rest of the production team.

The Time Schedule: Each and every production has a time schedule to keep before and after the production actually starts. Strict adherence to this schedule enables the production team to use their areas of expertise to bounce ideas off of each other in order to produce the best that each member can. The time schedule includes meetings that each of the heads of the team members are required to attend during which they discuss design details and hear the desires of the director for the production. Throughout the course of the numerous required meetings, there are due dates for the costume designer to follow.

1.6 Discussions of Findings

Creating a believable illusion through costume and set design is a very important aspect in a theatrical production. Every production in theatre is the culmination of a collaboration of creative individuals who each have a very explicit role to play. Part of the success of a production I appreciate your assurance regarding the copyright status depends on set designers, lighting coordinators, directors, producers, props masters, actors, etc. The idea is to create a believable new world that relates to the audience. The costume designer's job is to use all of the tools that are within their grasp to both research the best option for costuming and to actually construct the costumes. In order to do this, they must conduct research while working with the needs of the production team and the constraints that their products place on the costumes. The relationship between research, construction tools, and the abilities of creative peers gives the costume designer all that is needed to help define the characters in a production. All of these tools are used by the costume designer to polish off the character which helps to ensure the audience's correct interpretation of a production.

Costume is not just about clothing the performer; it is the process of studying who and what the character in the scripts is. In character description costume plays an important role because what the audience sees gives a more immediate impression of who the character is, than what he or she says; that is what they (the audience) hear from the characters speech. Consequently costume naturally gives a form of expression about an individual either of his or her social status, culture, religion, profession, sex, age and so on. It reflects in the daily life of the people because it is closely related with festivities, culture, pleasure, fashion and basic religious practices in Africa and the world over. This ability of dressing to make an impression about the wearer on an

onlooker is even more profound in the theatre because once a character appears on stage the audience instantly begins to interpret that character by what they see on him. In this respect, costume performs a primary role in helping the audience understand the character as well as his cultural background.

Thus, defining the character in a play or movie is an attempt to communicate with an audience a specific idea. The costume should be relevant to the time, feel, and character of the actor while still remaining subtle enough to not steal the show itself. Costumes are invaluable in providing information to the audience about the story and the character being presented, just like the set designed for a performance. The point of the costume is to be a part of the experience, sometimes bringing the audience back thousands of years and sometimes bringing them to a futuristic society that has not yet been realized. It is the goal of the designer to literally fabricate a new reality for the audience in their definition of the character in all of the ways aforementioned.

1.7 Summary and Conclusion

Since drama cum performance is a reflection of life, the role of the costume designer like the scenic designer in any stage performance is to be able to portray all the denotative and connotative meaning messages and their relevance as revealed in a play to educate the audience. In the theatre, costume and set designs are regarded as the main media of identifying and expressing the subjectmatter and thematic preoccupation in a play. The designer's greatest challenge therefore is to give visual forms to abstract ideas. To achieve this aim the designer must be familiar with the script. He / She must divorce herself / himself from his / her world of reality and be transported to the cultural world of the drama by understanding the philosophy and concept of the playwright.

Furthermore, the designer should be willing to experiment, relying on the desired atmosphere of the play to determine among others, the cultural milieu and suitability of the designs. To achieve these, the designer is expected to carry out research, read wide and arrange for oral interviews when necessary. These design requirements are evident in achieving the costumes and sets design for any Theatre production / performance.

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